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IMPLEMENTING PEER FEEDBACK IN PRACTICE – A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Formative feedback is well known as an effective learning tool [1] as it improves metacognitive competences and self-directed learning.

Peer feedback has been a learning activity used in higher education for many years and it involves feedback from one student to another student [2]. Peer feedback increases the amount of feedback for individual students and also strengthens the students' skills in giving and receiving feedback. However, peer feedback needs to be instructed and supported, for example by having rubrics and clear rules for how to provide feedback. One way to obtain this, it is to use the program Peergrade.io. The program Peergrade.io supports assignment submission and the feedback process itself. The system provides overview of the students' activity as well as their feedback process.

In this study, we investigated the implementation of peer feedback in an interdisciplinary course with focus on entrepreneurship. We discuss the theory behind peer feedback as a learning activity in teaching, discuss our findings from our case study and give suggestions for further use of peer feedback. We used the program Peergrade.io for peer feedback for evaluation of a portfolio based on the students' work with entrepreneurial methods. The data are reflections from the students after they had been giving and received feedback from fellow students.

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The results shows a positive attitude towards peer feedback and it was recognized as a good tool for feedback. However clear instructions and rubrics are important.

1 INTRODUCTION

Formative feedback is well known as an effective learning tool [1] as it can help students in developing self-knowledge and skills in assessing their own and other's contributions and thereby strengthen their metacognitive competences and self-directed learning.

Peer feedback can be an important alternative to formative assessment from the teacher as both giving and receiving feedback can promote the students learning, and the students become more aware of their own strengths and progress. Furthermore, peer feedback can also help to actively involve the students and engage them in the learning process.

Peer feedback involves the student evaluating a fellow student's work, ideally against a pre-defined standard like a rubric. A rubric is a guide that describes the specific criteria for a specific assignment. Its purposes are to give the students informative feedback about their works in progress [3]. The rubric can be defined either by the teacher alone or by the students together with the teacher. A rubric often contains both descriptions of the individual criteria and a level for division within each criteria.

Many benefits of peer feedback for student's learning have been described in the literature [4], [5]. However, peer feedback needs to be instructed carefully to the students and be supported for example by having rubrics. Furthermore, the students should be trained in giving and achieving feedback from fellow students [6].

Peergrade.io is an online platform to facilitate peer feedback sessions with students. The program Peergrade.io supports assignment submission and the feedback process itself. The system provides overview of the students' activity as well as their feedback process [7].

The peer feedback session in peergrade.io consists of the following steps:

- 1) Students submit their work online.
- 2) Students review each others work. The students give each other anonymous feedback through the rubric.
- 3) Students engage with their feedback. The students receive feedback from their peers, they react, discuss and engage with their feedback.
- 4) The teacher has a complete overview.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the implementation of peer feedback in an interdisciplinary course with focus on entrepreneurship.

We used the program Peergrade.io for peer feedback for evaluation of an individual portfolio based on students work with entrepreneurial methods. The data are reflections from the students after they had been giving feedback and received feedback from fellow students.

2 METHODOLOGY

The data was collected on a three week course held in August 2020, at the Technical University of Denmark's campus in Sisimiut, Greenland. The students came from three different programs and were mixed in groups of 3-4 students. After the first week of the course the students handed in an individual report (portfolio). The individual report concerned the methods which the students had used and reflected on upon using the methods (pros and cons, learning for next time etc.), where the maximum length of the report was set to five pages. The submission was done in the program Peergrade.io.

The peer feedback session consisted of four parts:

- 1) Introduction to peer feedback and introduction on how to give and receive feedback. A short introduction to what constructive feedback is and how to use the feedback afterwards was given.
- 2) The peer feedback session took place using the platform Peergrade.io. The rubrics consisted of four criteria. Two of them were standards (mention something your classmate did well and mention something your classmate could improve) and two were added (what to include more and what to reduce).
- 3) After the peer feedback session each student met with the teacher and reflected on the peer feedback session.
- 4) In the final report, each student reflected on the peer feedback session and results (learning).

Each student had two hours to read and to provide feedback to three fellow students. Afterwards each student received feedback from three other students and they had to respond to the feedback. Afterwards the teacher read the feedback and had a follow up meeting with each student.

At the end of the course, the students handed in a final report and part of the report consisted of a reflection part concerning the experience with peer feedback and what they had learnt from it.

3 RESULTS

Out of 15 students, 14 students submitted their report for peer feedback.

Part 1. Some of the students had tried to use peer feedback before, but for most of the students it was the first time. For all students, it was the first time they received

an introduction on how to give and receive feedback. For all the students, it was the first time they tried to use peergrade.io program.

Part 2. All students gave and received feedback on their assignment. Most of the students gave feedback on two-three reports; a few only on two reports (decided by the Peergrade.io program). It was fluctuating how much text the student wrote as feedback.

Part 3. At the subsequent feedback session with the teacher, it was mentioned that it had been very useful to see how other fellow students had approached writing the report. It was noted that the report setup and other students' use of figures and tables was inspiring and gave rise to consideration as to how they could do so themselves in future reports. All students were positive about peer-feedback and the use of the program peergrade.io.

In the final report, the students reflected on what they had learned from the peer feedback session. The summaries from the final reports show a generally positive attitude towards peer feedback. It was described as being an eye opener in relation to learning from each other and thereby be able to improve one's own work.

Here are some statements:

- *“Positive to see how other students have approached the same task”*

- *“I gained new views into methods that I had not used myself”*

- *“By reading two other students reports and giving feedback on these, I gained insight into how the task could be solved in other ways than the one I had chosen. This provides inspiration as well as respect for the fellow students different competencies”*

Furthermore, it was mentioned that it is appreciated to receive feedback from several fellow students who are on the same level as oneself (students). Anonymity at Peergrade.io meant that honest opinions were given which might be difficult to say face-to-face. Anonymity also blurred cultural differences. A few students mentioned that they were less positive at the beginning of the peer-feedback session and more positive after they had tried to give and receive feedback.

The results from this study shows that both giving and receiving feedback are perceived positively and that the students can see the value in this. Furthermore, the platform Peergrade.io proved an effectively tool for peer feedback. The introduction to the peerfeedback session was appreciated but could be extended for example by showing some examples from other peer-feedback sessions.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

By meeting with the students and hearing the students' descriptions of their own reflection in their final report, we gained insights into how the students' perceive peer feedback, and what worked for them and which challenges they experienced relating to peer feedback.

The Peergrade.io platform has proven to be a very useful tool for the peer feedback session.

This study is a small study which has provided some usefull results for optimizing the peer feedback session. Further studies with more students are needed for more thorough investigation into the method and tool; and it would also be interesting to further investigate letting the students create the rubrics themselves as part of the peer feedback process.

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